

The contribution of GIS for the sustainable protection of monuments: the case of Erimokastro and Sarantapixo acropolis in Rhodes, Greece

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Abstract. The use of GIS (Geographic Information System) as a tool for the analysis of all the diverse data gathered from a monument is of great importance. Through a GIS platform, the process of characterizing and classifying data, as well as their connection to various descriptive data is presented. The descriptive data consist of historical, architectural, structural documentation, material and decay patterns data, photographs, conservation interventions documentation, cost analysis data etc. Within the framework of the preservation of built cultural heritage, the utilization of GIS, monitoring the pathology and preservation state of a monument, contributes to decision making and planning of conservation interventions and rehabilitation of the area under study. In this paper, the process of the gathering and representing data from multidisciplinary studies through a GIS platform and the elaboration of thematic maps of the buildings pathology and conservation interventions in two cases, are presented, the case of Acropolis of Erimokastro in Rhodes Island and the case Acropolis of Sarantapixo in Rhodes. In conclusion, through the utilization of GIS in monuments, a dynamic multidisciplinary database is created, which can lead to its further management and conservation, aiming at the monitoring of the construction durability and sustainability. Finally, through this work it can be demonstrated that with the appropriate management of all these diverse data (data obtained from NDT & E techniques combined with spatial data) using AutoCAD and GIS, could permit the local authorities and others stakeholders to evaluate, assess and plan preservation strategies for the sustainable protection of the monuments.

1. Introduction

In this paper, the process of the gathering and representing data from multidisciplinary studies through a GIS (Geographic Information System) platform and the elaboration of thematic maps of the buildings pathology and conservation interventions are presented. In general, the monitoring and preservation of heritage monuments is based on various kinds of investigations and analytical data [1]. Investigations are carried out in order to diagnose the monuments current state of conservation and future restoration interventions [2]. In the work described, a multidisciplinary approach was applied for the damage rehabilitation of the archaeological site of Erimokastro Acropolis and Sarantapixo Acropolis in Rhodes, Greece. The Acropolis of Erimokastro (Deserted Castle) is an established archaeological site, located upon a natural hill between Kallithea and Afantou bays. Its dry-stone walls are multifaceted and possibly of cyclopean type ‘figure 1’. The Acropolis of Sarantapixo is not an established archaeological site, even though there is strong evidence that it was protected by cyclopean walls of the Mycenaean period, and their remains are still evident throughout the site. It is situated in the northeastern part of Rhodes ‘figure 2’.

Figure1: The Entrance of Erimokastro Acropolis

Figure2: The Wall of the Sarantapixo Acropolis

2. Documentation

In the Acropolis of Erimokastro and the Arcopolis of Sarantapixo, selected facades were depicted for the documentation. This approach included: (a) a combination of close range photogrammetric and field survey techniques, and (b) the characterization of building materials and decay diagnosis, using nondestructive techniques in situ and analytical techniques in the laboratory, after sampling [3]. The collected data were incorporated into a GIS platform creating a relational database. The ortho-rectified images ‘figure 1’, ‘figure 2’ were used as the GIS base-map, where data elements in space were recorded. The diagnostic study results comprised the information data about building materials and decay patterns. GIS thematic maps of building material and decay patterns were elaborated, presenting characteristic parts of Erimokastro Acropolis and Sarantapixo Acropolis.

The geometric documentation was accomplished with the use of terrestrial measurements and the use of photogrammetric methods in both archaeological sites, providing the necessary qualitative and quantitative information. A total station along with GPS measurements was used for the topographic field measurements. The selected areas of the Acropolis of Erimokastro were a characteristic façade of the walls (north oriented façade) ‘figure 1’ and part of the wall at the entrance of the Acropolis (east oriented façade) ‘figure 3’. For the Acropolis of Sarantapixo, part of the remaining north wall was depicted (west oriented wall) ‘figure 2’. These parts of the walls were chosen because they are characteristic architectural elements of both sites are representative of the building materials used and the decay patterns developed are accessible, and their orientation variance or similarity could be used for a reliable comparative study.

Figure3: Characteristic part of the Wall in Erimokastro Acropolis

Furthermore, on the wall facades, non-destructive testing and evaluation techniques were applied in situ, whereas analytical techniques were used in lab after sampling, resulting in building materials characterization and decay diagnosis for both investigated sites [4]. In addition, materials and conservation interventions were suggested according to the results of the integrated diagnostic study.

3. Results and Discussion

As the data acquisition resulted, the analysis of the facades proceeded and all the diverse data were imported to a GIS platform for both investigated monuments. In order the GIS relational operations to be provided, topology of the data is a prerequisite. Topology of the diverse data is initially built with the creation of layers in the CAD environment. In addition, data retrieval and queries is accomplished with the GIS management and analysis tools [5].

The attribute dataset consisting of building materials and decay patterns of the wall, resulting from the physicochemical analysis, was imported and aggregated to the attribute dataset created in the CAD environment, containing topological (i.e. perimeter, area, etc.) and descriptive characteristics from the technical report of the strength of the materials, recorded and attributed to the spatial entities, thus, interrelated with the vector data. In the case of Erimokastro Acropolis, the thematic maps of building material and decay pattern are presented ‘figure 4’, ‘figure 5’.

Figure4: Building materials and decay thematic map for the entrance

Figure5: Building materials and decay thematic map for the wall

In the case of Sarantapixo, the thematic map of the building material and decay patterns of the depicted wall, where corresponding layers classification and mapping was performed, including all the different kind of materials and decay patterns which were identified by the diagnostic study, is presented ‘figure 6’.

Figure 6: Building materials and decay thematic map for the wall of the Sarantapixo Acropolis

The materials and their decay were characterized using an array of non-destructive techniques validated and supported by a series of analytical methods after sampling. Previous to any conservation intervention applied on the selected facades, a diagnostic study was required to provide the data for the selection of compatible materials and techniques.

The conservation interventions / restorations thematic maps resulted from the geoprocessing analysis in the GIS platform from the materials and decay patterns thematic maps. The features consist of additional attribute data from both input and overlay themes (material / decay). Using the geoprocessing tool of GIS platform, the resulting features include combined spatial properties and attribute data of the decay patterns, additionally classified according to new attribute data sets regarding the suggested materials and conservation interventions. Consequently, each material and conservation intervention is represented by a different layer and is displayed by a different color in the conservation interventions thematic maps ‘figure 7, figure 8’, ‘figure 9’.

Figure7: Conservation interventions thematic map for the wall of the Erimokastro Acropolis

Figure8: Conservation interventions thematic map for the entrance of the Erimokastro Acropolis

Figure9: Conservation interventions thematic map for the wall of the Sarantapixo Acropolis

4. Conclusion

Protection of cultural heritage requires the preservation of the monuments that are most of the times deteriorating abandoned and left to decay for years and for decades. Thus, preservation of cultural heritage requires a versatile multidisciplinary planning that should be focused on the pathology of the monument and its documentation and on the other hand on compatibility in conservation intervention in terms of sustainability. In the case of Erimokastro Acropolis the diagnostic study results (building materials and decay data) were recorded and attributed to the selected façades which could be applied throughout the entire archaeological site. The same procedure was followed in the case of Sarantapixo Acropolis. GIS modeling provides information about the monument's building materials in the façade of the walls and the extent of decay patterns, as well as the degradation of the building materials regarding their location (proximity of the sea, orientation of the façade, rising dampness etc.). Furthermore, with the GIS analysis tools, on the developed material/decay and conservation interventions/ restorations thematic maps, the monitor of the preservation state of the monument under study, can be achieved and the management of the monument's materials life cycle as well as the proposed restoration materials can be evaluated leading to its sustainable protection. Finally, through the management of all these diverse data, data obtained from NDT & E techniques regarding damage assessment on cultural heritage and conservation strategies combined with spatial data, integrated into spatial oriented tools (AutoCAD and GIS), an opportunity is provided to the local authorities and stakeholders to evaluate, assess and plan preservation strategies for the sustainable protection of the monuments.

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